

Holistic Progress Card: Assessing Implementation Feasibility in Government Primary Schools of Manipur, India

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ABSTRACT

This research explores the feasibility of implementing the Holistic Progress Card (HPC) in government primary schools in Manipur, India, which aligns with the National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020) objectives. The HPC aims to provide a comprehensive assessment framework for students, encompassing academic, social, emotional, creative, and vocational domains, moving away from traditional rote learning practices. The study employs a descriptive survey methodology, collecting data from 10 government primary schools in the Imphal West district, Manipur. The key focus areas include teaching methodologies, availability of resources, assessment tools and techniques, challenges in implementation, and stakeholder recommendations for the HPC adoption process. The findings indicate

a predominantly positive attitude among school headteachers and teachers toward the HPC, demonstrating a willingness to transition to this innovative assessment system. However, significant challenges have been identified, such as inadequate pedagogical resources, limited technological access, and financial constraints. Resistance among some educators, stemming from concerns over increased workload and the complexity of the new system, also poses a potential barrier. The research emphasizes the necessity of comprehensive teacher training programs to build capacity in formative assessment practices and tool utilization. Additionally, it highlights the critical role of parental and community engagement in ensuring the success of the HPC implementation. The study concludes that while there is foundational readiness for introducing the HPC, addressing the identified challenges through targeted strategies—such as phased implementation, continuous professional development, and enhanced resource allocation—is essential for its successful adoption in Manipur's primary schools.

Introduction

Education reforms in India have been significantly shaped by the National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020), which emphasizes holistic development and competency-based assessments. One of the key initiatives under this policy is the introduction of the Holistic Progress Card (HPC), designed to assess students across multiple dimensions, including academic, social, emotional, and vocational skills (NCERT, 2021). The implementation of the HPC in primary schools aims to shift the focus from rote memorization to a more comprehensive evaluation of student progress.

The National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020) marks a significant shift in India's educational landscape, emphasizing critical thinking, creativity, and holistic development over traditional rote memorization. The NEP's primary goal is to achieve universal foundational literacy and numeracy by 2026-27. This necessitates moving from traditional assessment methods to a more competency-based

approach. The Holistic Progress Card (HPC) is a key initiative under this policy, designed to provide a 360-degree assessment of students' progress, covering academics and social, emotional, creative, and vocational growth.

The HPC has been developed by the National Assessment Centre PARAKH (Performance, Assessment, Review, and Analysis of Knowledge for Holistic Development, 2021) and NCERT to align with the NEP's objectives. However, the successful implementation of the HPC across diverse educational contexts like Manipur requires a thorough examination of the ground realities, including teaching practices, resource availability, and stakeholder attitudes. This study focuses on the feasibility of implementing the HPC in the primary schools of Manipur, with a specific focus on the Imphal West district.

The rationale of the study

The success of any educational reform, including the HPC, depends on its implementation at the grassroots level. Given India's diverse socio-economic and cultural landscape, it is crucial to assess the readiness of schools to adopt such reforms. In the context of Manipur, where educational infrastructure and resources vary widely, understanding the challenges and opportunities for implementing the HPC is vital.

This study is motivated by the need to provide empirical evidence on the feasibility of HPC implementation in Manipur. By focusing on the readiness of schools, the study aims to identify gaps in resources, training, and stakeholder engagement that may hinder the effective adoption of the HPC. The findings will inform policymakers, educational administrators, teachers, and all the stakeholders, helping them make evidence-based decisions aligned with the NEP 2020 goals.

Operational Definitions of Key Terms

- **Holistic Progress Card (HPC):** A comprehensive, multidimensional report card that assesses students' development across academic, social, emotional, creative, and vocational domains, in line with the NEP 2020.
- **Competency-Based Assessment:** An evaluation method that focuses on students' ability to apply knowledge and skills rather than simply recalling information, promoting higher-order thinking skills.

- **Foundational Literacy and Numeracy:** Students are expected to master basic reading, writing, and arithmetic skills at the foundational stage of education.
- **Formative Assessment:** An ongoing assessment process that provides continuous feedback to improve students' learning and development.
- **Rote Memorization:** A learning technique that focuses on memorization without understanding the underlying concepts, often criticized for not promoting critical thinking or problem-solving skills.

Review of Literature

The literature surrounding the implementation of the HPC highlights several critical themes:

1. **Competency-Based Education:** Research by **Bingham et al. (2021)** emphasizes the importance of competency-based education (CBE) in fostering students' critical thinking and problem-solving skills. The shift from traditional assessment methods to a more holistic approach aligns with global educational trends.
2. **Teaching Practices:** **Parker and Thomsen (2019)** identify effective pedagogical strategies that promote holistic learning, including play-based and experiential learning. These methods are crucial for engaging students and fostering a deeper understanding of the curriculum.
3. **Resource Availability:** According to the **OECD (2017)**, the availability of resources significantly impacts the successful implementation of educational policies. Effective teaching and assessment require adequate infrastructure, training, and materials.
4. **Stakeholder Attitudes:** **Fullan (2021)** highlights the role of stakeholder buy-in in educational reforms. Understanding the perceptions of teachers, parents, and school leaders is vital for ensuring the successful adoption of new initiatives.
5. **Challenges in Implementation:** **Anderson (2011)** points out that communication gaps and inadequate training can hinder the implementation of educational reforms. Addressing these challenges is essential for fostering a supportive environment for change.
6. **Holistic Assessment Frameworks:** **Andrade and Cifuentes (2011)** found that holistic assessment practices improve student engagement and motivation, reinforcing the importance of implementing comprehensive evaluation systems like the HPC.

7. Parental Involvement: Research by **Epstein (2018)** emphasizes the significant role of parental involvement in educational success. Engaging parents in the HPC implementation process can enhance its effectiveness and acceptance.
8. Cultural Context: Studies by **Creswell and Pothkam (2018)** highlight the importance of tailoring educational reforms to fit local cultural contexts. Culturally responsive practices are essential for successful implementation in a diverse region like Manipur.
9. Professional Development: **Darling-Hammond et al. (2020)** stress the need for ongoing professional development for teachers to implement new educational practices effectively. Training programs should focus on innovative pedagogies and assessment techniques that align with the HPC.

Objectives of the Study

1. To explore the methods of teaching alignment with the HPC framework used by the teachers in classroom transactions.
2. To identify the supportive resources available for teaching and learning that can facilitate the effective implementation of the HPC.
3. To examine the assessment tools and techniques currently used by teachers and their compatibility with the HPC.
4. To determine the challenges and suggestions for implementing the Holistic Progress Card effectively.

Research Methodology

The study employs a descriptive survey method with a purposive sampling technique.

Population and Sample

The study was conducted in 10 government primary schools in Manipur's Imphal West district. These schools were selected using purposive sampling based on their participation in the pilot phase of the HPC. The sample included five rural and five urban schools, ensuring a balanced representation of different educational contexts within the district. The respondents comprised two teachers and one headteacher. This resulted in 30 participants from the 10 government primary schools of Imphal West district of Manipur.

Tools Used

The study used two self-made questionnaires as a tool.

- i. **School Questionnaire for Headteachers:** This tool was designed to gather data on the availability of resources and the challenges faced during its implementation.
- ii. **Teacher Questionnaire:** This tool focuses on understanding the teaching methods, assessment tools and techniques, and challenges towards the HPC.

Statistical Techniques

The data was analysed using qualitative methods. Quantitative data were tabulated and presented in graphical formats, with a percentage method employed to interpret the data. Qualitative data were analysed using thematic content analysis, identifying recurring themes and patterns from the responses.

Delimitations of the Study

The study was limited to 10 government primary schools in the Imphal West district of Manipur, India. The study also focused primarily on the perspectives of school headteachers and teachers.

Analysis and Findings

A. Objective 1: Teaching Methods Used by Teachers in Classroom Transaction

Under objective 1, the present study focuses on the uses of teaching methods and pedagogies by Teachers in Classroom Transactions, focusing on their relevance to implementing the HPC. It primarily focuses on the pedagogy aligned with LOs or curricular goals. It uses learner-centred pedagogies like play-based learning, project-based learning, activity-based learning, role play, projects, quizzes, feedback, etc., to develop the holistic development of students.

Table 1: Analysis of Responses of Teachers on the Present Teaching Methods

Sl. No.	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	Teaching based on LOs and curricular goals.	0%	0%	0%	79%	21%

2	Using the lecture method only	7%	57%	15%	21%	0%
3	Incorporate activity-based learning	0%	0%	21%	43%	36%
4	Integration of play-based learning	0%	0%	7%	64%	29%
5	Incorporation of experiential learning	0%	0%	0%	71%	29%
6	Adapting teaching to students' ability, pace, and learning styles.	0%	0%	0%	43%	57%
7	Employing inquiry, exploratory, and discovery learning methods	0%	8%	7%	64%	21%
8	Usage of mother tongue/local language for instruction	0%	0%	0%	71%	29%
9	Integrating different methods, like role play, quizzes, dramatics, etc., are used to teach concepts.	0%	0%	36%	50%	14%
10	Undertaking informal assessment for feedback and improvement.	0%	0%	7%	86%	7%
Overall Mean Percentages		1%	6%	8%	61%	24%

The analysis of the study on pedagogical practices and teachers' responses (Table 1) to implementing the Holistic Progress Card (HPC).

- 1) 79% of teachers focus on teaching based on learning objectives and curricular developmental goals.
- 2) There's a mixed response to the lecture method, with 21% agreeing or strongly agreeing, while 57% disagree with its exclusive use.
- 3) Activity-based learning through group work and projects is widely supported (79% agree or strongly agree).
- 4) Play-based learning using games, toys, art, and music is highly favored (93% agree or strongly agree).
- 5) Experiential learning, involving real-life connections and fieldwork, is unanimously endorsed (100% agree or strongly agree).
- 6) All teachers (100%) adapt their teaching methods to students' abilities, pace, and learning styles.

- 7) Although most respondents (85%) use inquiry-based learning, a small percentage (7%) either disagree or remain neutral, which could indicate either resistance to or challenges in implementing this method.
- 8) Teaching in the mother tongue or local language is strongly supported (100% agree or strongly agree).
- 9) The use of diverse teaching methods like role-play, quizzes, and dramatics is acknowledged by 64% of teachers.
- 10) Informal assessment for progress identification and positive feedback is widely practiced (93% agree or strongly agree).
- 11) Overall, 85% of teachers agree or strongly agree that they use progressive pedagogies aligned with HPC techniques.

The findings indicate a generally positive attitude among teachers towards student-centred and holistic pedagogical practices. While there's room for improvement in some areas, most teachers are committed to using diverse, experiential, and adaptive instructional approaches to meet curricular goals and address students' diverse needs.

Figure 1: Distribution of Teachers on Teaching Methodology Used by Teachers in Classroom Transaction

The overall analysis of methods of teaching alignment with the HPC framework used by the teachers in classroom transactions shows that 61% agree and 24% strongly agree that they use progressive pedagogies for HPC-aligned techniques. Only 1% and 6% strongly disagree or disagree.

While more training and support may be needed in specific areas, most teachers are committed to using holistic, experiential, and adaptive instructional approaches to meet curricular goals and address diverse student needs.

B. Objective 2: Available Supportive Resources of Teaching and Learning for HPC Implementation

Objective 2 focuses on studying the available resources for teaching and learning to implement HPC in schools. It primarily examines whether there are sufficient resources such as educational tools, technology access, supportive staff, financial resources, communication mechanisms, and platforms for storing and sharing students' progress. The table below shows the availability of these resources from the perspectives of school heads.

Table 2: Analysis of available supporting resources for teaching and learning

Sl. No.	Statement	Response from School Heads				
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	Availability of sufficient pedagogic and assessment tools.	0%	43%	28%	29%	0%
2	Accessibility to Appropriate Technology	29%	43%	14%	14%	0%
3	Supportive teachers and staff	0%	0%	29%	57%	14%
4	Financial support for HPC implementation	0%	86%	14%	0%	0%
5	Mechanism for regular communication	0%	14%	29%	57%	0%
6	Having secure and accessible resources for storing students' progress	0%	0%	43%	43%	14%
Total Mean Percentage		4%	23%	27%	38%	8%

The analysis of school heads' responses (Table 2) regarding the availability of resources for implementing the Holistic Report Card (HPC) in schools.

1. Insufficient pedagogic and assessment tools (43% disagreement)
2. Inadequate technology access (72% disagreement)
3. Strong availability of supportive teachers and staff (71% agreement)
4. Lack of financial support (86% disagreement)
5. Effective communication mechanisms in place (57% agreement)
6. Mixed opinions on secure platforms for storing student progress

Overall, there's a moderate alignment with resource availability (46% total agreement), but significant challenges remain. The analysis concludes that addressing these issues is crucial for successful HPC implementation.

Figure 2: Distribution of responses of School Heads on the Availability of Supportive Resources

School heads' responses on HPC resource availability show mixed perspectives: 46% positive (38% agree, 8% strongly agree), 27% neutral, and 27% negative (23% disagree, 4% strongly disagree). At the same time, slightly more view resources as adequate, significant uncertainty and concerns exist. This indicates room for improvement in resource allocation for HPC implementation.

C. Objective 3: Assessment tools and techniques used by the teachers towards HPC

Objective 3 focuses on the study of assessment tools and techniques teachers use, examining if they are aligned with the Holistic Progress Card (HPC) implementation. It covers aspects such as

assessment nature, tools, feedback mechanisms, documentation, and the focus of progress cards. The following tables show the assessment tools and techniques related to the responses of Teachers.

Table 3: Analysis of Assessment Tools and Techniques used by teachers

Sl. No.	Statement	Responses of Teachers				
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	Assessment across domains	0%	0%	15%	71%	14%
2	Usage of self-assessment or peer-assessment	0%	36%	21%	43%	0%
3	Usage of observation as a tool	0%	15%	14%	71%	0%
4	Incorporating varied assessment methods	0%	7%	36%	57%	0%
5	Usage of rubrics and checklists	0%	29%	57%	14%	0%
6	Recording progress using Anecdotes and Portfolios.	0%	29%	43%	28%	0%
7	Recording progress using portfolios	0%	29%	35%	36%	0%
8	Assessment mode – summative or formative assessment.	0%	7%	29%	64%	0%
Total Mean Percentage		0%	19%	31%	49%	1%

The analysis of teachers' perspectives on assessment tools and techniques relating to the Holistic Progress Card (HPC) implementation. Key findings include:

- 1) Strong agreement (71%) among teachers on assessing students across cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains
- 2) Limited use of self-assessment and peer assessment (36% disagreement among teachers)
- 3) Wide adoption of observation as an assessment tool (71% agreement among teachers)
- 4) Use of diverse assessment methods (57% agreement among teachers)

- 5) Use of rubrics and checklist (57% neutral, and 29% of teachers disagree)
- 6) Recording progress using anecdotes and portfolios (29% of teachers disagree)
- 7) Recording progress using portfolios (36% agreeing and 29% disagreeing)
- 8) Assessment mode in the form of formative and summative assessment (64% of teachers agree that both of them are used)
- 9) Overall, 49% agree with these assessment practices, but there is notable neutrality (31%) and some disagreement (19%).

The analysis concludes that while there's general alignment with HPC principles, some gaps persist in assessment practices. Targeted professional development could help bridge these differences and further improve HPC implementation.

Figure 3: Distribution of Responses of Teachers on Assessment Practices

The analysis of teachers' responses (Table 3) regarding assessment practices for the Holistic Progress Card (HPC) implementation reveals that 49% agree with the effectiveness of current tools, while 31% remain neutral. A smaller percentage, 19%, disagree, and only 1% strongly agree. The results suggest mixed perceptions, with general support but room for improvement.

E. Objective 4: Challenges faced by the head teachers and teachers in using Holistic Progress

Card:

Objective 4 focuses on the challenges of implementing the Holistic Progress Card (HPC), including teacher resistance, workload, time constraints, parental involvement, alignment of teaching

and assessment, data collection and analysis, engagement with parents, secure storage of student progress data, and financial constraints. School heads and teachers' responses are given below.

The analysis of school heads' perspectives on challenges in implementing the Holistic Progress Card (HPC). Key findings include:

- 1) Potential teacher resistance to shifting from traditional report cards (57% agreement)
- 2) Concerns about increased teacher workload and time constraints (43% agreement)
- 3) Challenges in involving parents and the community (43% agreement)
- 4) Unanimous agreement (100%) on teachers' difficulty aligning teaching and assessment across domains
- 5) Issues with data collection, analysis, and documentation in HPC format (43% agreement)
- 6) Challenges in maintaining regular communication with parents (57% agreement)
- 7) Concerns about secure data storage of student progress (57% agreement)
- 8) Financial constraints as a significant obstacle (71% agreement)

The overall mean response indicates moderate alignment with perceived challenges (45% total agreement). The analysis concludes that schools recognize potential challenges and must address them through targeted training, effective communication strategies, and financial planning to ensure successful HPC implementation.

The analysis of teachers' perspectives on challenges in implementing the Holistic Progress Card (HPC). Key findings include:

- 1) Strong need for more knowledge about HPC components (93% of teachers agree)
- 2) Challenges in collecting and tracking student progress across domains (86% and 79% of teachers agree, respectively)
- 3) Difficulties using various pedagogies and assessment tools (64% of teachers agree)
- 4) Challenges in documenting student progress (71% of teachers agree)
- 5) Limited resources in schools (86% of teachers agree)
- 6) Concerns about personalized assessment in large classrooms (64% of teachers agree)
- 7) Communication challenges with parents and community (79% of teachers agree)

The analysis concludes that addressing systemic and classroom-level barriers through comprehensive training, resource allocation, and community engagement initiatives is crucial for successful HPC implementation.

Several challenges were identified in the implementation of the HPC. The most significant challenges included:

- **Teacher Resistance:** 57% of headteachers reported resistance among teachers towards shifting from traditional report cards to the HPC, mainly due to concerns about increased workload and the complexity of the new assessment system.
- **Resource Constraints:** Both headteachers and teachers highlighted the lack of adequate resources, particularly pedagogic tools and technology, as a significant barrier to implementing the HPC.
- **Data Management:** 57% of headteachers expressed concerns about the challenges of collecting, analyzing, and securely storing student progress data in line with the HPC requirements.

Suggestions and Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study offers several recommendations to facilitate the successful implementation of the Holistic Progress Card in Manipur's primary schools:

1. **Enhanced Training Programs:** Providing comprehensive training programs for teachers and school headteachers focused on the HPC framework, particularly on using diverse assessment tools and methods, is crucial. Training should also address integrating formative assessment practices and using data for student progress tracking.
2. **Resource Allocation:** Adequate resources, including pedagogic tools, technology, and financial support, should be allocated to schools to ensure they can effectively implement the HPC. This may involve seeking external funding or partnerships with private organizations to bridge resource gaps.
3. **Stakeholder Engagement:** Effective communication strategies should be developed to engage parents and the broader community in the HPC implementation process. This could include regular meetings, workshops, and information sessions to ensure all stakeholders are informed and involved in the assessment process. Engaging parents is particularly crucial as their involvement can significantly enhance the effectiveness of the holistic approach promoted by the HPC. Schools should also consider creating platforms for continuous feedback from parents, which can help refine the assessment process and address any concerns.

4. **Ongoing Support and Collaboration:** Establishing support networks among teachers, headteachers, and education administrators can facilitate the sharing of best practices and collaborative problem-solving. Regular workshops, peer learning sessions, and online forums can effectively maintain momentum and address challenges as they arise during the implementation of the HPC.
5. **Data Management Systems:** Given the challenges related to data collection, analysis, and secure storage, schools should invest in reliable data management systems that are easy to use and align with the requirements of the HPC. Training teachers and administrative staff on these systems is equally important to ensure accurate and efficient management of student progress data.
6. **Pilot Programs and Phased Implementation:** To mitigate the challenges of a full-scale rollout, it may be beneficial to implement the HPC in phases, starting with a pilot program in select schools. This approach allows for identifying and resolving potential issues before expanding the program to more schools. Lessons learned from the pilot can inform the broader implementation strategy, making it more effective and sustainable.

Conclusion

The feasibility study on implementing the Holistic Progress Card (HPC) in Manipur's primary schools reveals optimism and challenges. While there is a strong foundation of readiness among educators, as evidenced by their generally positive attitudes toward the HPC, significant obstacles must be addressed to ensure its successful adoption.

Resource constraints, including the availability of pedagogic tools, technology, and financial support, emerge as critical barriers. Moreover, the need for comprehensive training programs to equip teachers with the necessary skills to implement competency-based, formative assessments cannot be overstated. Effective stakeholder engagement, particularly involving parents, is another area that requires focused attention.

A phased implementation strategy, supported by pilot programs and ongoing professional development, is recommended to move forward. Schools must also establish robust data management systems to handle the demands of holistic progress tracking. With these interventions, the HPC can potentially transform assessment practices in Manipur's primary schools, aligning them with the broader goals of the NEP 2020 and fostering a more holistic, student-centred approach to education.

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